

Acidity Functions of Indicators for High pH Range in Non-aqueous Media. Part-III

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Acidity function concept was first proposed by Hammett and Deyrup¹. H^m -scale for solutions of lithium sodium and potassium methoxides are reported². α -(*o*, *m*, *p*) Hydroxyphenylazo-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanides behave as acid-base indicators and the transition of colour lies in high pH range³. Their acidity functions were studied in ethanolic sodium ethoxide media (ese).

Results and Discussion

Three indicators reported, exist as a molecular species in acidic media and their absorption maxima are in the range 410–430 nm. The extinction coefficients

of the *ortho* (OHPNBC), *meta* (MHPNBC) and *para* (PHPNBC) compounds in ethanol lie between 9×10^4 and 1.4×10^5 . The *ortho* and *para* compounds show well defined isobestic points. There may not be any side-reactions and that there is equilibrium between two species only. At higher pH, monoionic species are converted to dianionic ones. At very high pH, di-ionic species are exclusively present. Di-ionic species in all cases exhibit absorption bands in longer wave length region. Usually the plot of absorbance versus pH is a linear parallel to pH axis. Once 100% di-ionic species are formed the linear relation between absorbance and pH is not expected and thus lowering of the molar absorptivity does not significantly affect the useful range of indicator. No considerable change was observed in stock solution over a period of one year. The pK_1 and pK_2 values are given in Table 1.

Acidity functions were calculated on the basis of

TABLE I

Compd.	λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , 10^4 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)			Colour change	Iso-bestic point		Ioni-sation constant		Acidity function	
	Molecu-lar species	Mono-anionic species	Di-anionic species		1	2	pK_1	pK_2	H^E	H_2^E
OHPNBC	430 (3.4)	535 (3.9)	610 (6.7)	Yellow to red to violet	460	580	15.22	17.92	19.25	17.36
MHPNBC	420 (9.2)	620 (1.4)	570 (1.9)	Yellow to green to blue	440	460	19.50	18.00	13.14 to 16.59	18.43 to 19.97
PHPNBC	430 (6.4)	520 (4.2)	600 (2.3)	Yellow to red to violet	460	540	16.63	18.47	16.03 to 16.52	17.38 to 19.37

use of autoprotolysis constant of ethanol⁴. H^m - and H_2^m - values were calculated from spectra of indicators in methanolic sodium methoxide. The values agree with theoretical ones.

These azo indicators are used to define new scales for measuring acidity properties in ethanolic sodium methoxide in highly alkaline media.

Experimental

Indicators were prepared by diazotising the aminophenols. α -(*o*-Hydroxyphenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide was prepared by taking α -(*o*, *m*, *p*)-aminophenol (B.D.H.) (1.09 g, 10 mmol) and dissolving 25% HCl (50 ml). The solution was cooled in an ice-bath. Sodium nitrite (0.7 g) was added in one lot. A solution of *p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide (PNBC) (1.62 g, 10 mmol) in ethanol (110 ml) was added to the amine solution and the mixture was stirred for 5 min, filtered and the filtrate was neutralised with 1*N* NaOH. The resulting solid was purified chromatographically, m.p. 167.5° (Found : C, 59.3; H, 3.2; N, 10.5%). The azo compound was found soluble in water, moderately soluble in ethanol and stable.

Absorbance was measured on a Carl-Zeiss Spekol

spectrophotometer using 10 mm glass cuvettes and pH was measured⁵ using Philips G404 pH meter. Ionisation was studied by standard method⁶. Ionisation constants were determined by using Henderson equation,

$$pK_a = pH \pm \log \frac{A_i - A}{A_i - A_m}$$

where, A_i is the absorbance at higher pH, A the absorbance at chosen intermediate and A_m the absorbance at lower pH.

References

1. L. P. HAMMETT and A. J. DEYRUP, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 2721.
2. R. SCHAAL and G. LAMBERT, *J. Compt. Rend.*, 1962, **255**, 2256; F. PEURE and R. SCHAAL, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1963, 2636.
3. R. SCHAAL and R. LAMBERT, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1962, 1164
4. R. A. MORE, O'FERRALL and J. H. RIDD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 5030.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., ELBS, London, 1968, p. 166.
6. W. STENOTROM and N. J. GOLDSMITH, *Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 1683.